

Strategic use of Social Media to Screen Job Applicants – a Review of the Benefits, Concerns and Best Practices

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Abstract

Purpose

This paper examines the role of social media in screening job seekers. As social media sites have gained popularity in recent times, organizations are able to access large amounts of professional and personal information of job applicants. This information is used primarily to narrow the applicant pool, but concerns exist regarding the appropriateness of using such practices. The author identifies several best practices that can increase the effectiveness and reliability of using social media as a source of applicant data.

Design/methodology/approach

The author reviewed relevant literature and research on the use of social media websites to screen applicants, identifying the benefits of such practices, along with its costs.

Findings

This paper aims at further developing our understanding of strategically using social media for applicant screening purposes and the implications of such practices. The author points out both the positive and negative aspects of using social media as a screening tool, with the hope that practitioners will use the information from job seekers' social media pages in an unbiased and non-discriminatory manner.

Originality/value

This paper provides guidelines regarding appropriate utilization of social media as a screening tool as part of an organization's recruitment and selection process.

Keywords: Social media; Screening Tool; Equal Employment Opportunity; Bias; Discrimination.

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Why Use Social Media as a Screening Tool?

The Resource Based View theory (RBV) (Barney, 1991) proposes that sustainable competitive advantage can be achieved by acquiring resources that are valuable, rare, inimitable, and difficult to substitute. The strategy literature draws on the RBV to explain how qualified and skilled human resources can lead to improved organizational performance, and subsequent sustained competitive advantage (Hatch and Dyer, 2004). Ultimately, the success of an organization hinges largely on its ability to recruit the right person for the job, which involves the collection of reliable information on job seekers.

As the popularity of social media (SM) has increased over the years, more and more organizations are turning to such services to screen applicants. A recent Jobvite (2021) survey reported that 30% of recruiters are using SM to collect information about job seekers. SM channels used most by recruiters are Facebook (68%), LinkedIn (65%), Twitter (48%), Instagram (46%) and YouTube (35%). The increased use of these sites to screen applicants could be attributed to the fact that SM presents several advantages compared to traditional recruitment and selection activities.

For instance, SM provides easy access to a large amount of public information about applicants that may not be readily obtained using traditional hiring tools such as resumes, applications, interviews etc. Since screening of SM content does not require applicant consent or input, such information can be speedily and cost-effectively collected to perform **background checks** to address negligent hiring concerns. It also provides employers the opportunity to verify

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3 applicant information that had already been provided. Depending on the SM site, the personal
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5 and/or professional information gleaned can also be used to assess applicants' cognitive ability,
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7 criminal behavior, skills, professionalism, prior work experience and personality traits to
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9 determine **person-job** and **person-organization fit**. In fact, studies have demonstrated that
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11 personality assessments using SM information may be more accurate than self-rated assessments
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13 done during traditional hiring processes (Kluemper, 2013). In addition, organizations are turning
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15 to professional SM sites such as LinkedIn to scour through **passive candidate** profile to identify
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17 qualified potential employees to extend job offers to. SM sites have also enabled organizations to
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19 reach out to a **young generation** of job seekers.
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24 However, organizations are also using SM to narrow the applicant pool by unearthing
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26 **negative information** that may make a candidate unsuitable for the job. Employers are less
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28 likely to hire candidates whose SM profiles are rife with spelling and grammatical errors, flaunt
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30 inappropriate posts or photographs, display evidence of criminal activities, or include references
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32 to marijuana and alcohol consumption (Jobvite, 2021).
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37 Nevertheless, the strategic use of SM to screen applicants necessitates organizations be
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39 aware of the possible downsides of using such practices, since the improper use of SM can incur
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41 costs that may be greater than the benefits stemming from these services.
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44 **Potential Pitfalls of Using Social Media for Screening Candidates**

45 *Privacy Issues*

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47 Most SM sites have privacy settings that users can customize, ranging from open access
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49 to highly selective, restricted previews. Depending on the privacy settings, SM can supply
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51 organizations with a large variety and amount of applicant information; however, any attempt to
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3 access information can ultimately raise privacy concerns. To illustrate, Slovensky and Ross
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5 (2011) found that job seekers consider it an invasion of their privacy if organizations gather
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7 information that is personal in nature, and unrelated to work. There also have been reports of
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9 employers demanding candidate's SM login information during the application process for
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11 vetting purposes, but such extreme intrusive acts are likely to reduce applicant's goodwill and
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13 trust towards the organization as a potential employer. As such, several states in the US have
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15 passed laws that prohibit such practices. For example, in New Jersey it is illegal for an employer
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17 to ask for a job applicants' (this law also protects current employees) login details to their
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19 personal SM sites. If any potential employer violates this law and requests access to personal
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21 social media account(s), applicants can refuse and report to New Jersey's Labor Commissioner
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23 and the law will protect them from retaliation or discrimination from employers.
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29 *Bias and Discrimination Concerns*

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32 Despite the numerous benefits of using SM as a hiring tool, such sites may inadvertently
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34 provide organizations with information that are protected for employment purposes. For
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36 example, the American with Disabilities Act (ADA) prohibits employers from discriminating
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38 based on an applicant's disability. Similarly, the Equal Employment Opportunity Commission
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40 (EEOC) makes it illegal for employers to discriminate based on an applicant's religion, national
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42 origin, race, color, or sex. While employers cannot legally inquire about these characteristics in
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44 an interview, such sensitive information can be easily collected from SM sites, and qualified
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46 applicants may be prevented from obtaining jobs if employers make biased hiring decisions
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48 based on such personal information. The EEOC have long encouraged organizations to only
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50 collect job-relevant information, but the mere exposure to sensitive information in SM sites may
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52 bias employers towards or against an applicant.
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Reliability of SM information

Research suggests that the huge amount of information in SM sites can lead to information overload – employers may not be able to cognitively process all relevant information, leading them to rely on mental shortcuts and cognitive biases (Van Iddekinge *et al.*, 2016) – this calls into question the validity of using SM data for hiring purposes. Furthermore, job seekers may actively attempt to bias employer perceptions by posting only positive information to present themselves in a favorable light, and arguably some are better at it than others. Such impression management activities involve removing all negative content from SM pages, modifying appearance using filters, or even hiring professional firms to erase any controversial information present online. In addition, the information in SM pages may not accurately reflect an applicant’s personality and behavior, because how an individual behaves at work could be entirely different from the way they conduct themselves in their private social circles, which again calls into question the reliability of SM data.

The amount of information posted in SM also varies based on characteristics such as gender. Zide *et al.*, (2014) demonstrated that women were less likely than men to post recommendations and professional interests in LinkedIn. Another possible problem of relying on SM data is that multiple profiles may exist for people with similar names. Employers may reject a candidate based on the information found on the profile of a mis-identified person. Finally, an applicant’s SM profile may be contaminated by posts from others that the applicant has no control over, which may cause employers to evaluate the applicant negatively.

Recommendation for Organizations

(a) *Better Train Artificial Intelligence (AI) Models*: Many organizations are using AI based algorithms to review employee data in resumes and application materials. As 'Big Data' is accumulated over time from SM profiles, AI should be better trained to use the data to evaluate candidates' skills and qualifications in an equitable and bias free manner.

(b) *Only Use Professional SM Sites*: Studies (Bowen *et al.*, 2021) suggest that applicants are more comfortable with organizations collecting information from professional SM sites such as LinkedIn, since the information provided is directly related to the applicant's job-related qualifications and experiences. Research also suggests that bias exists regarding how SM is used to evaluate candidates – professional SM sites are utilized more often to elicit positive information, while personal SM sites are used to collect negative information (Hartwell and Campion, 2019). Thus, it might be best for organizations to evaluate candidates based on professional SM data.

(c) *Be Transparent About Hiring Practices and Policies*: SM screening policies should not be intrusive and should be transparent regarding how the information is to be collected and used. Permission should be sought from applicants prior to data collection. All related labor laws should be followed, and strict guidelines should be developed to ensure that information is collected consistently across all levels, from the same sources. Collected information should be securely stored and maintained.

(d) *Complement Traditional Hiring Practices with SM screening*: Using SM to screen employees is a fairly new practice, and the legal and ethical guidelines for using such practices are still evolving. Unless a transparent, efficient, ethical, and legal process is not developed, SM to

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3 screen applicants is not likely to replace traditional recruitment and selection practices – in fact,
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5 SM should be used in conjunction with such practices. It is recommended that organizations
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7 collect applicant data from SM only after the first round of interviews, so as to not develop any
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9 biases or preconceived notions prior to direct communication with the candidate.
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12 13 **Concluding Thoughts** 14 15

16 To win the “War for Talent” (Elving et al., 2013), organizations are increasingly relying
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18 on SM to gather information about potential employees. However, there exists ethical, legal, and
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20 methodological concerns regarding these practices. This article reviews recent research and
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22 highlights the benefits and costs of using SM and provides recommendations to guide
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24 practitioners and academics alike regarding the collection of applicant data for recruitment and
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26 selection purposes.
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